

Practical Life : Efforts To Train Independence In Early Children

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explain Practical life activities in an effort to train early childhood independence through habituation. This type of research is descriptive qualitative which is directed towards narrative studies. The participant in this research was a class teacher at As-Syuhada Kindergarten, Wargo Mulyo Village, Kapuas Kuala District, Kapuas Regency. The results and findings of the research are that there are learning strategies in implementing practical life activities in an effort to train early childhood independence with the following steps: 1) Teachers provide repetitive activities (habituation) to early childhood, 2) Teacher preparation for learning to train children's independence early age, 3) Effective teachers are able to create a cheerful learning atmosphere and attract attention in an effort to train early childhood independence, 4) Creative teachers in an effort to train early childhood independence. However, during the implementation of Practical Life, during break times, children wash their hands before eating, there is a lack of hand washing facilities and infrastructure because only one hand washing facility is used in 2 classes between Kindergarten A and Kindergarten B, so the children - children scramble to wash their hands. Even at that time, the teacher's preparation was still not able to see the situation and provide a quick solution to provide easy facilities such as providing water in another tub so that there was no fighting over it and not directing children to be disciplined in queuing.

INTRODUCTION

Age early is an important time for child For get developments that with exists giving stimulation from environment around Children are very influential big For future life. Age child early is children who are in the range aged 0-6 years (Khaironi , 2018). At age the development brain in children is being highly optimized, because child age early need own specialized education for help child. Age child early different with adults, pattern he thought showed past expression and behavior his behavior. Sharpness Power think appeared in self child show that child age early have potency For built , formed nor given something learning or education available optimizing all over potential and can attached to life next (Sari, DY, 2018). This is very important For become priority because in stages age early child is at in the golden age where children Already start develop various abilities and skills in look after himself yourself . This is also very consistent with opinion Yusutria & Febriana , (2019) that development independence in children age early who have 5-6 years old , ability Already reached the stage capable do the task becomes not quite enough he answered Alone like cleaning and tidying up place play , obey rule class , capable arrange self yourself , and can responsible answer on his behavior For kind self yourself . Besides That Maria Montessori's view of education child age early is education provided _ For children 0-6 years did it in the environment school with material Skills daily use method outward and inward giving _ freedom child For choose desired activities and media used. Activity self that leads to formation discipline personality , independence , and direction self . So from That one way with opinion on that one _ Competence basic principles instilled in children is attitude independent . As on the website www.indonesiamontessori.com on the site the explain about Skills life or often called (Practical life skills) which is one curriculum Montessori approach to child age early . Like activity wash hand before and after food , washing advance as well as method get dressed etc. _ Activity This too simple for adults because We Already often do it , meanwhile for child age early This is very new thing for them. Because of that with apply activity Skills live , son expected can more believe self and respect himself yourself , from attitude trust and appreciate self Alone here it is independence child will appeared .

On the Law Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning The National Education System in Article 1 paragraph 14 states that education child age early is something effort targeted coaching _ to child since born until with age six year carried out through giving stimulation education For help growth and development physically and spiritually for children own readiness in enter education more continued (Ministry of National Education , 2003). With exists education child age early with via 3 routes that is formal education , non - formal education and informal education place child age early For develop various aspect like religious and moral values , physical motoric , cognitive , language , social emotional and artistic . One _ Early Childhood Education institutions on non-formal channels are Group Play (KB) which is education child 3-4 years old or called with child age preschool works For help growth

and development child to child own readiness in enter education more carry on specifically Kindergarten level . _

Early Childhood Education is also an an integral part of education in a way whole aim For develop all aspect development child age early . In accordance with uniqueness and growth child age early so organizer education for child age early customized with stages development that children go through age early . One _ objective education child age early is embed independence in children since early . Need exists the role of the teacher in implement and strive child age early in practice independence children on Pratical Life.

Based on description the researcher _ want to know more in about independence child . So from That done research entitled " Practical Life : Effort Practice Independence in Early Childhood

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Practical life

Defenitin of practical life

Children gain knowledge from various ways, in accordance with one of the characteristics of early childhood, namely that children are active individuals, so more knowledge is obtained from experience carrying out various activities. With the existence of early childhood education in schools, there is learning that is implemented in a targeted manner so that young children can be trained by getting used to it through practical life . According to Rantina (2015), practical life is a direct daily life activity in the learning process of providing life skills to children in increasing children's independence. Meanwhile, Morisson (2012: 111), writes that practical life is an activity that emphasizes daily motor activities, such as walking from one place to another in an orderly manner, carrying objects such as trays and chairs, learning self-care skills, maintaining cleanliness. and carry out other practical activities.

Practical life is a daily life activity directly in the learning process of providing life skills (life skills) to kindergarten age children in increasing children's independence (Isjoni, 2009: 128).

1. Practical Life Goals

The aim of developing Practical Life in children is to display the totality of understanding in everyday life, both in kindergarten and in the wider environment (family, friends, community). The field of Practical Life development includes aspects of moral development and religious values, as well as social, emotional and independence development. The aspect of moral development and religious values aims to increase children's devotion to God Almighty and develop children's attitudes in order to lay the foundation for becoming good citizens. Meanwhile, aspects of social, emotional and independent development aim to develop children so that they can control their emotions naturally and can interact well with each other and adults and help themselves with life skills (Ministry of National Education, 2007:2). It was

explained that the aim of developing Practical Life for children is to (Ministry of National Education, 2007:3):

1. Be aware or recognize the desired behavior in everyday life.
2. Tolerating a variety of behaviors that reflect a diversity of values.
3. Accepting desired behavior and rejecting undesirable behavior is good by oneself or others.
4. Choose behavior that reflects desired values, for example discipline, independent, polite, friendly, respectful and respectful of others.
5. Internalize good values as part of the personality that guides daily behavior.

Children's Independence Understanding Independence

Watson & Lindgren, 1979, "independence means the freedom to take initiative, overcome obstacles, do things correctly, be persistent in efforts, and do everything yourself without relying on help from others. This independence is one of the important aspects that every individual child must have which can help him achieve his life goals, achievements, success and gain awards. All of these achievements must be supported by an independent nature. If he is not supported by an independent nature to achieve something optimally, it will also be difficult for him to achieve success . Independence is an individual attitude acquired during development, where individuals will continue to learn to be independent in dealing with various situations in the environment, so that individuals are able to think and act on their own. A person's independence can choose their path in life to develop more steadily (Mu'tadin, 2002) .

According to (Hurlock 1991) independence is the ability to carry out daily activities or tasks alone or with little guidance, according to the stage of development and capacity. The earlier the child is able to practice independently in carrying out developmental tasks, it is hoped that independent values and skills will be easier to master and can be firmly ingrained in the child.

Kartini and Deli (Irene, 2007: 10) who say that independence is the desire to do everything for oneself. In short, it can be concluded that independence means:

1. A situation where children have a competitive desire to move forward for their own progress.
2. Able to take decisions and take initiative to overcome the problems faced.
3. Have confidence in doing the tasks.
4. Be responsible for what you do.

Characteristics of Independent Children

Children who have the characteristics of independence according to Masrun (2006: 10), namely a child who allows himself to act freely, do things based on his own encouragement and needs, pursue achievements, are full of perseverance and the desire to do everything without help from other people, are able to think and act originally, creatively, are able to overcome the problems they face, are able to control their actions, are able to influence the environment, have confidence in themselves, appreciate their own circumstances and obtain satisfaction from their efforts. This opinion is reinforced by Sri Yuniati (Satmoko, 2008: 37) who states that independence consists of several aspects, namely: 1) Emotions, demonstrated by the ability to control emotions and not being dependent on the emotional needs of parents. 2) Intellectual, demonstrated by the ability to face the problems faced. 3) Social, demonstrated by the ability to interact with other people and not depend on or wait for action from other people.

Factors that Influence Independence

There are various factors that can influence the level of independence, namely:

1. Physical and psychological maturity,
2. Personality traits, and
3. Cultural demands.

Personality characteristics that influence a person's level of independence include intelligence, motivation, interests, emotions (Irene, 2007: 13).

Nakita (2005: 36) states that when the abilities that a child should have mastered at a certain age are in fact not willing or able to do so, it can be categorized as that the child is not yet independent. Moreover, there are many factors that influence children's independence, such as congenital factors, parenting patterns, physical condition and birth order. The level and characteristics of each child's independence are different, so parents must be more sensitive in determining guidance patterns for their children.

Relevant Research

Edi Sulis Purwanto's research in 2009, the results showed that teachers' efforts to train early childhood independence were through example and habituation. By example, teachers always give concrete examples to children to develop good mental attitudes in students, such as praying before and after lessons. With habituation, teachers practice habits carried out at school such as practicing and learning fine motor skills and being disciplined.

METHODS

Sample

Participants in this research a teacher at T k A s -S yuhada Wargo Mulyo Village, Kapuas Kuala District, Kapuas Regency. With the criteria of being a teacher who is still actively teaching and has been a homeroom teacher for more than 5 years. The time for conducting the research is May 2022.

Research design

This research was carried out to explain practical life activities in an effort to train early childhood independence. This type of research is descriptive qualitative narrative study. This narrative research is a typical form of qualitative research, focusing on the study of one person or a single individual who gives meaning to their experience through the stories told, data collection which can be done by collecting stories, where there is individual reporting, individual experiences, discussing meaning. the experience is for the individual. (Cresswell, 2012).

Data collection technique

Data collection is carried out by:

1. Observation (Observation)

Researchers field and make notes that can be used in data collection. The prepared format contains study variables and indicators so that field notes are focused and do not deviate from the study objectives.

2. Interview

After making field notes, continue conducting interviews and collecting respondents' answers to each study question to find out whether there are the same or contradictory answers and so on. If there are conflicting answers, a narrative or reason is created.

3. Documentation

By mapping the respondents' answers, conclusions can be drawn that can answer the objectives of the study. After the study conclusions have been prepared, the policy options will continue to be prepared based on the study conclusions that have been made and documented.

Data Analysis

The data analysis used in this research uses qualitative data analysis activities also proposed by Miles in Sutanta (2019), which consists of:

1. Data reduction, the results obtained during the research so that it can be seen how teachers' strategies train young children's independence in carrying out Practical life.
2. Data presentation is carried out after the data obtained has been reduced. Data is interpreted in the form of words and language so that it is organized and can be understood well.
3. Drawing conclusions from a collection of data that has been collected and allowing conclusions to be drawn.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Stages of Implementing Practical Life in an Effort to Train Children to be Independent.

To find out more about how to implement Practical Life in an effort to train children to be independent at an early age. Based on the results of

interviews at Kindergarten. As-Syuhada has a process of activities carried out as follows:

1. Teachers provide repetitive activities (habituation) to young children .

According to Anis Ibnatul M, et al (2013: 1) say that habituation is an activity that is carried out repeatedly so that the activity can become a habit. Habituation is a form of learning that is trained repeatedly to familiarize individuals with behaving, behaving and thinking correctly. Where the process of habituation produces experience, while what gets used to is something that is practiced. At Kindergarten school. As-Syuhada, Kindergarten A's homeroom teacher, in the morning before starting learning, there is a routine activity every morning which raises the enthusiasm of the children by having a cheerful greeting between the teacher and students (morning recoling) before the teacher starts the learning activities so the children come to school and are welcomed. The homeroom teacher in front of the classroom door gives directions to the children to prepare for the beginning of learning by reading a prayer and directing their friends to lead, in the middle of the lesson using puzzle media, children are given an explanation of how to assemble a picture puzzle, give a reward if someone has finished putting it together, Give sweet persuasion to attract children and direct them. We give them an example of tidying up the media that has been finished and placed in another media collection place.

2. Preparation Teachers learn to train children's independence.

Preparation is the act of (things etc.) getting ready or preparing; design (action) for something (Poerwadarminta, 1984). According to Slameto (2012:59) teaching readiness is "the teacher's readiness to teach is closely related to the way the teacher prepares students to learn". When the learning activity ended, the children had entered break time and the class A teacher prepared meals together during the break. The teacher immediately directed the children to wash their hands before eating. When children are washing their hands, there are some children who have difficulty reaching the water tap, because the place for washing their hands is not adapted to the child's body posture. As a result, children who don't have it will have difficulty doing it, making it difficult for the child to do it. The teacher immediately prepared a small ladder for the children to climb easily. However, there are still difficulties, namely children fighting over each other because there is only 1 hand washing place in the school out of several classes between Kindergarten A and Kindergarten B.

3. Effective teachers are able to create a cheerful learning atmosphere and attract attention in an effort to train early childhood independence.

According to Darhim (1997), an effective teacher is a teacher who can motivate students to learn and increase enthusiasm for learning which grows from students' self-awareness, not because they are afraid of the teacher. When the kindergarten class teacher. A provides material about the lesson on the theme of independence. Teachers provide learning media facilities by preparing interesting media and providing fun teaching techniques such as making small quiz games that encourage them to take initiative and be creative.

4. Teachers are creative in their efforts to train early childhood independence.

Supardi (2013:87) states "A creative teacher is a teacher who always has lots of ideas, lots of resourcefulness, lots of ideas to overcome something that is considered lacking or does not exist. For example, creative teachers can use used items as teaching aids or media and create crafts or skills." In Kindergarten. As-Syuhada, his teacher, was very creative and found many media made from used goods or from nature, such as cars made from noodle boxes, aqua bottles, while media from nature, such as leaves, could be used as painting or craft tools, such as hats, dolls, leaves, and print. From this media, teachers can easily train their independence by modeling how to make it using materials that are very easy to obtain so that children are very enthusiastic about making it too.

Practical Life Exposure in Efforts for Children to Train Their Independence.

The role of the teacher or environment is very important in supervising, guiding, directing and providing permanent role models which are very necessary, so that children remain in conditions or situations that do not endanger their safety. Based on the results of interviews with Kindergarten A homeroom teachers, there are findings from Practical Life. In the efforts of children to train their independence when carrying out learning, there are the following steps:

1. Teachers provide repetitive activities (habituation) to young children.

With activities in the morning (morning recoling) from the Kindergarten A homeroom teacher and while the learning is taking place, the Kindergarten A homeroom teacher gives rewards, gives sweet persuasion to interest the children and directs them by giving examples to them of tidying up the media that has been completed and placed in the group area. other media when learning ends. This activity looks like the children are very cheerful and are very used to the morning greetings given by the teacher in front of the class. This teaches children the meaning of good manners and their habits from the start of school in the morning and learning is carried out with the independence of young children in mind.

2. Teacher preparation in learning to train early childhood independence.

When children carry out hand washing activities, there are some children who have difficulty reaching the water tap, because the place for washing their hands is not adapted to the child's body posture. As a result, children who do not have difficulty doing so will find it difficult for the child to do it. The teacher immediately prepared a small ladder for the children to climb easily. However, there are still difficulties, namely children fighting over each other because there is only 1 hand washing place in the school out of several classes between Kindergarten A and Kindergarten B. It can be seen that there is a lack of facilities and infrastructure for hand washing places so that children are fighting over each other to wash their hands . Teacher preparation is still not able to see the situation and provide a quick solution to provide easy facilities such as providing water in another tub so that they don't fight over it and they haven't taught children to be disciplined in queuing.

3. Effective teachers are able to create a cheerful learning atmosphere and attract attention in an effort to train early childhood independence.

When the kindergarten class teacher. A provides material about the lesson on the theme of independence. Teachers provide learning media facilities by preparing interesting media and providing fun teaching techniques such as making small quiz games that encourage them to take initiative and be creative. In this activity, it was very clear that children with quizzes aroused their enthusiasm for learning and self-confidence to highlight their creativity in taking quizzes.

4. Creative teachers in an effort to train early childhood independence.

In Kindergarten. As-Syuhada's teacher is very creative, it was very visible when the researchers conducted observations and interviews that many media were found made from used goods or from nature, such as cars made from noodle boxes, hanging flower pots made from aqua bottles, while the media came from nature. like leaves, they can be used as painting or craft tools, such as hats, leaf dolls, and printing. From this media, teachers can easily train their independence by modeling how to make it using materials that are very easy to obtain so that children are very enthusiastic about making learning media and this discussion can also be used as an educational game tool (APE).

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